

IDENTIFICATION AND AUTHENTICATION IN INFORMATION SECURITY. NETWORK DISPLAY TECHNOLOGY

Abduraximov Ozodbek Azimjon o'g'li

Tojidinov Azizbek Ilhomjon o'g'li

Nazirjonov Ubaydulloh Nozimjon o'g'li

Muhammad Al- Khorazmi TATU in the name of Fergana branch student

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Abstract: Each subject registered in the computer system (user or process acting on behalf of the user) is associated with information that uniquely identifies it. It can be a number or a string of characters that names this subject. This information is called the subject identifier. If the user has an identifier registered in the network, he is considered a legal (legitimate) user, otherwise an illegal (illegal) user. Before using computer resources, the user must go through the identification and authentication process of the computer system. This article explains about this process.

Keywords: Identification, Authentication, Authorization, Accounting, Password, Dynamic, Virus

Identification - is the process of identifying the user by his identity (name). This is the first function that is executed when a user tries to access the network. The user informs the system of his identity upon his request, and the system checks its existence in its database.

Authentication - is the process of verifying that a given user, process, or device is real. This verification allows the user (process or device) to be sure that it is the real user. During authentication, the verifying party makes sure that the verified party is real, and the verified party also actively participates in the process of information exchange. Usually, the user confirms his identity by entering his unique information (for example, password or certificate) into the system.

Identification and authentication are interconnected processes of identifying and verifying that entities (users) are real. The permission of the system to use the system resources of a specific user or process depends on them. After identification and authentication of the subject, its authorization begins.

Authorization - is the process of granting certain powers and resources to the subject in the system, that is, authorization determines the scope of the subject's actions and the resources it uses. If the system cannot reliably distinguish an authorized person from an unauthorized person, the confidentiality and integrity of information in the system may be violated.

Authentication and authorization processes are closely connected with the process of managing user behavior.

Administration (Accounting) - recording of the user's activity in the network, including his attempts to use resources. This reporting information is critical for security disclosure, analysis, and appropriate response to network security incidents.

When protecting data transmission channels, it is necessary to perform mutual authentication of entities, that is, mutual confirmation of the authenticity of entities communicating through communication channels. Verification of authenticity is usually carried out at the beginning of the session, in the process of connecting subscribers to each other. The term "connection" means a logical connection between two entities of the network. The purpose of this procedure is to ensure that the connection is made with a legitimate entity and that all information reaches its intended destination.

A password is something that the user and their communication partner know. Passwords can be exchanged between a user and their partner for mutual authentication. Personal identification number (PIN) is a proven method for authentication of plastic card and smart card holder. PIN - the secret value of the code must be known only to the owner of the card.

A dynamic (one-time) password is a password that is used once and will never be used again. In practice, a regularly changing value based on a constant password or a passphrase is usually used.

Computer viruses and mechanisms to combat them.

What is it and how to fight it? Dozens of books and hundreds of articles have been written on this topic. Thousands of professional anti-virus experts are working in many companies. This topic is very difficult and requires a lot of attention. Computer virus remains one of the main reasons for data loss. Viruses are known to cause many organizations and companies to fail. There is information that in one of the Dutch hospitals, the patient died as a result of the medicine consumed according to the diagnosis made by the computer. It was the work of a computer virus.

A computer can quickly get infected with a virus if it is done carelessly. If a person is infected with a disease virus, it is expected that there will be a change in temperature, a change in weight, weakness and the appearance of pain. In computers infected with computer virus, the following are observed: program performance slows down, file sizes change, abnormal and some unknown errors, loss of data and system files. Some viruses multiply harmlessly, but not

dangerously. These viruses display error information on the screen. However, one type of virus is an attacker, that is, one that leaves bad complications. For example, viruses delete data on a hard drive.

What is a virus?

Virus means "infectious beginning", "bad beginning - destructive beginning", "infectious disease" in English.

One of the famous "doctors" D.N. Lozinsky compares the virus to a secretary. If we assume an orderly secretary, he comes to work and sees a stack of papers on his desk that he has to do in a day. He duplicates one sheet and puts one copy for himself and the other on the table next to him. The secretary at the next table also copies at least two copies and passes them to another secretary. As a result, the first copy in the office becomes several copies. Some copies can multiply and move to other tables.

Computer viruses work roughly like this, only papers are now replaced by programs, the secretary is a computer. If the first command is "move-copy", the computer will do it and the virus will spread to other programs. If the computer runs an infected program, the virus can spread to other programs and take over the entire computer.

If it takes 30 seconds for one virus to multiply, after one hour it can exceed 1000000000. More precisely, it can take up free space in the computer memory.

In order for a virus to be created, a sequence of executable codes must be formed under certain conditions. One of the properties of a computer virus is to copy itself to executable objects over computer networks. These copies are also capable of self-replication.

How are computer viruses created?

Unlike biological viruses, computer viruses are created by humans. Viruses cause great damage to computer users. They stop the computer or delete data on the hard drive. A virus can enter the system in several ways: data carriers, CD-ROM loaded with software, network interface or modem connection, global Internet; e-mail on the network.

It is easy for a data carrier to be infected by a virus. When a data carrier is inserted into an infected computer, a virus enters the head sector of the disk.

The Internet provides a great opportunity for information exchange. However, it creates a good environment for computer viruses and malware to spread. Of course, not all information obtained from the Internet contains a virus. Most specialists and operators working on a computer always check incoming data for viruses. Good antivirus protection is essential for anyone who works on the

Internet. According to the statistics of Kaspersky Lab's technical support service, 85% of virus infections occurred via e-mail. Compared to 1999, today this figure is 70%. Kaspersky Lab notes that e-mails need good antivirus protection.

Email is very convenient for virus writers. Practice shows that many viruses are created for popular programs, operating systems, and data transmission technologies. Currently, e-mail remains the main means of communication in business and other fields. That's why virus writers are focusing on e-mail.

There are many definitions of a computer virus. The first definition was given by Fred Cohen in 1984: "A computer virus is a program that infects other programs by inserting itself or a modified copy into them, modifying them. In this case, the introduced program retains the ability to reproduce." The ability of the virus to self-replicate and modify the computing process are the basic concepts in this definition. These features of a computer virus are similar to the parasitism of biological viruses in living organisms.

Currently, a computer virus is a software code that has the following characteristics:

- the ability to create copies that do not necessarily correspond to the original, but have the characteristics of the original (self-recovery);
- the presence of mechanisms that ensure the inclusion of created copies in the executable objects of the computing system.

It should be noted that these features are necessary, but not sufficient. The specified features should be complemented by the features of destructiveness and non-disclosure of the effects of harmful programs in the computing environment.

Viruses can be classified according to the following main symptoms:

- living space;
- operating system;
- performance algorithm feature;
- destructive capabilities.

Classification of computer viruses according to their habitat, in other words, the type of computer system objects into which viruses are introduced, is the main and widespread classification.

Categorization of computer viruses by location.

File viruses are inserted into executable files in various ways (the most common types of viruses), or create file companions (companion viruses) or use the feature of organizing file systems (link viruses).

Bootable viruses write themselves in the boot sector of the disk (boot sector) or in the sector that is the system bootloader (Master Boot Record) of the

Winchester. Download viruses act as program code that takes control at system boot.

Macroviruses infect macro programs and files of modern information processing systems, in particular, MicroSoft Word, MicroSoft Excel, etc. poisons the files and spreadsheets of mass editors such as

Network viruses use computer networks and e-mail protocols and commands to spread themselves. Network viruses are sometimes referred to as "worm"-like programs. Network viruses are divided into Internet worms (spread over the Internet), IRC worms (chats, Internet Relay Chat).

The execution cycle of computer viruses usually includes five stages:

1. Loading the virus into memory.
2. Search for the victim.
3. Poisoning the found victim.
4. Performing destructive functions.
5. Transfer control to the virus program carrier.

Viruses are self-propagating viruses. They do not harm the system, they just use free disk space.

Safe viruses - viruses associated with various impressions (sound, video) in the system, while reducing free memory, do not harm programs and data.

Dangerous viruses - viruses that cause serious defects in computer operation. As a result, the program and data may be corrupted.

Very dangerous viruses - viruses that directly lead to the destruction of programs and data and the deletion of information necessary for computer operation, the processing of which is placed in advance processing algorithms.

Transferring control to the virus-carrying agent. It should be noted that viruses are divided into destructive and non-destructive ones. Malicious viruses do not care about maintaining the functionality of programs when they are infected, so this step is meaningless to them.

Anti-virus monitoring. The essence of this method is that there is always an anti-virus program in the computer memory that monitors suspicious actions performed by other programs. Anti-virus monitoring allows you to check all programs that are run, documents that are created, opened and saved, files of programs and documents downloaded from the Internet or copied from a diskette or any CD-ROM. The anti-virus monitor will notify the user if any program tries to perform a dangerous action.

A method that detects changes. Using this method, called a disk checker, the antivirus program remembers all areas of the disk that can be attacked in

advance, and then periodically checks them. When a virus infects computers, it changes the contents of the hard drive: for example, it adds its own code to a program or document file, adds a program-virus call to the Autoexec.bat file, changes the boot sector, creates a folder. By comparing the values of the characteristics of the disk sectors, the anti-virus program can detect changes made by known and unknown viruses.

Installing anti-virus tools in the basic input/output system (BIOS) of computers. Simple means of protection against viruses are installed on the system board of computers. These tools allow you to control all accesses to the master boot record of hard disks and the boot sectors of disks and diskettes. If any program tries to change the contents of the boot sectors, the protection is triggered and the user is warned. But this protection is not very reliable.

Referens:

1. Muxtarov, F., & Tojidinov, A. (2023). Tarmoq xavfsizligini url filtirlash bilan yaxshilash. Research and implementation, 1(4), 39-44.
2. Muxtarov, F., & Sadirova, X. (2023). Korxonada axborot xavfsizligini ta'minlashning zamonaviy usullari. Engineering problems and innovations.
3. Muxtarov, F., Turdimatov, M., & Mominova, M. (2023). Umumiy o'rta ta'limga kiberxavfsizlik fanini tizimli isloh qilishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari. Engineering problems and innovations.
4. Muxtarov, F., Umarov, A., & Ro'zaliyev, A. (2023). Axborot tizimlarida xavfsizlik tahdidlarining tasnifi. Engineering problems and innovations.
5. Рахимджон, Х. (2022). 6 Новых языков программирования, которые стоит изучить. Academicia Globe: Межнаучные исследования, 3 (04), 126–135 стр.
6. Umaraliyev, J., Abdurakhimov, O. AN ARTICLE ON THE PROGRESS OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN SOCIETY. SCIENCE, EDUCATION, CULTURE AND INNOVATION, 2(6), 15-17.
7. Stop it son, UJ., Azimjon son, AO. , & Ilhomjon daughter, IS. (2023). THE TRANSFORMATIVE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF TELECOMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN OUR DAILY LIVES. ONLINE - CONFERENCES; PLATFORM, 138–139. Retrieved from
8. <http://papers.onlineconferences.com/index.php/titfl/article/view/1260>
9. Umaraliyev, J., Abdurakhimov, O., & Isokjonova, S. (2023, June). USE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN MEDICINE. In Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education (Vol. 1, No. 11, pp. 148-151).

10. Umaraliyev, J., Turdaliyev, K., Isoqjonova, S., & Abdurakhimov, O. (2023). ITS APPLICATIONS AND PROSPECTS IN EDUCATION. Interpretation and Researches, 1(11). search the horse
11. <http://interpretationandresearches.uz/index.php/iar/article/view/1277>

